

ESiWACE 2 - WP4

Using XIOS to manage ensemble simulations with the IPSL-ESM model

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Abstract

Ensemble simulations are used to better estimate the uncertainty of climate model results. The production of ensemble simulations with current IPSL model requires to run independently as many simulations as there are members in the ensemble, producing a very large number of inodes as a consequence of writing files for each member. In 2022, we have developed a functionality that allows several simulations to be carried out simultaneously, all simulation writing its results in a common single file. This new functionality has required developments in IPSL's XIOS IO server (in its version 2) in order to handle an additional "ensemble" dimension in the result file, as well as in OASIS coupler to provide MPI inter-communicators for all of the coupled members. The IPSL libIGCM runtime environment library was also adapted to manage efficiently the use of different types of files (forcing, parameters, restart, results) by several members within the same computing job. This job allows now "by itself" to simultaneously perform simulations of several members of an ensemble. The number of files resulting from these ensemble simulations matches (without any post-processing step) with criteria required by computing centers filesystems. Finally, the results of all the members of an ensemble are available in a single file, thus facilitating statistical processing and scientific analysis. This development is used in several IPSL scientific applications : the reconstruction of paleoclimate and historical periods by data assimilation methods and the simulation of extreme events (heat waves) in Western Europe.

1. IPSL model

The IPSL Earth System Model (IPSL-CM6A), in its ocean-atmosphere version, is composed of LMDz (atmosphere model), ORCHIDEE (land surface model) and NEMO (ocean model including sea ice and marine biogeochemistry) components. This coupled model allows the realization of a range of climate simulations: assembled or autonomous components, coarse or fine scales, simulations from a few months to several centuries. It has been intensively used to produce the CMIP6 simulations and to generate data requested by the CMIP6 Data Request : this data production has been done on the fly thanks to the dr2xml and XIOS tools, so that the data can be

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directly published after writing by the XIOS servers. OASIS3-MCT is used as coupler to allow exchange and interpolation between ocean and atmosphere components. The models runs on CPU architectures and computing machine used for the tests of this work is the TGCC supercomputer Irene-Rome, AMD Rome comprising 2,286 nodes, 292,608 cores. The model runs on MPMD mode and the parallelization of the atmospheric component LMDZ is a hybrid MPI/OpenMP parallelization while the parallelization of the ocean component NEMO and the XIOS server is MPI only.

2. Several members of IPSL model

Ensemble simulations consist in running several instances (or members) of the model in parallel. The current IPSL model works in such a way that each member produces its own output files (Figure 1), and thus, in the case where several instances of the model are launched, many inodes are provided.

Figure1 : One instance of IPSL model

Consequently, the constraints imposed by the computing centers in terms of maximum inode quotas are quickly reached. One solution is to perform a post-processing step to gather the output files to reduce the inode footprint. This post-processing step is very heavy in terms of temporary buffer size, computing resources as well as time to solution. Another solution is to adapt the model so that it is able to write the data of all the members in one single file, which therefore contains an additional “ensemble” dimension, whose size corresponds to the number of members. It is this approach that we choose to explore: it requires of course modifications from the ESM components (atmosphere, land use, ocean) but also both the OASIS coupler and the XIOS I/O server.

2.1. General philosophy

The objective is to execute each member of the ensemble simultaneously and independently, but with the possibility of writing in a single file. To avoid each member interacting with each other in an uncontrolled manner, it is advisable to first

isolate their execution in separate directories, with the input files specific to each member for starting-up: restart files, parameters files, forcing files and XIOS xml files. To avoid unnecessary duplication, identical and unmodified files will be symbolically linked. Only the XIOS output files will be common to all members and will therefore be located in a single directory visible to all members.

Although each member is fundamentally independent of the others, this is not the case from the XIOS point of view, which considers all the members of a single component as a single 4-D model, with the usual horizontal (2-D) and vertical (1-D) dimensions plus an additional ensemble dimension, each member providing a data slice corresponding to its own member index number. To do this, each member component must have its own MPI communicator allowing it to perform its internal communications and to couple via OASIS to the other component of the same member. However, within the same component, all the members must have a common MPI communicator to make calls to XIOS, which must be done as collective calls by all the component's processes for all the members. All this is illustrated by figure 2.

Figure 2 : Handling of MPI communicators in 2 instances of IPSL model

2.2. Components modifications

The changes to be made to each component are fairly minor. Previously, each component retrieved its MPI communicator through a call to XIOS during initialisation. From now on, the returned MPI communicator is that of all the members. It is then necessary to split this communicator so that each member recovers its own communicator. Example for the LMDZ code:

```
CALL wxios_init(model_id, outcom=COMM_LMDZ_ENSEMBLE)
CALL MPI_COMM_RANK(COMM_LMDZ_ENSEMBLE,ensemble_comm_rank,ierr)
CALL MPI_COMM_SPLIT(COMM_LMDZ_ENSEMBLE, ensemble_pool_member_rank, &
                    ensemble_comm_rank, COMM_LMDZ, ierr)
```

The second part of the modifications will concern the creation and management of the new ensemble dimension, which will be implemented through the management of XIOS :

```
IF (ensemble_management)                                &
  CALL xios_set_axis_attr("ensemble",n_glo=whole_ensemble_size, &
                        begin=whole_ensemble_rank, n=1)
```

On this occasion, it is also necessary to slightly modify the XIOS XML files for each of the components so that the output grids become 4-D grids and no longer 3-D grids: e.g:

```
<grid id="grid_glo_plev">
  <domain domain_ref="dom_glo" />
  <axis axis_ref="plev" />
  <axis axis_ref="ensemble" value="_reset_"/>
</grid>
```

becomes :

```
<grid id="grid_glo_plev">
  <domain domain_ref="dom_glo" />
  <axis axis_ref="plev" />
  <axis axis_ref="ensemble" value="_reset_"/>
</grid>
```

The last changes concern coupling via OASIS for which each component must be identified by its member number in order to communicate with the appropriate member of the other component.

All the changes to the LMDZ model (atmosphere) can be seen here:

https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/igcmg/changeset?reponame=&new=6208%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodeles%2FLMDZ&old=5501%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodeles%2FLMDZ

Those of the ORCHIDEE model (land use):

https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/igcmg/changeset?reponame=&new=6166%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodeles%2FORCHIDEE&old=5501%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodeles%2FORCHIDEE

And those for NEMO (ocean) :

https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/igcmg/changeset?reponame=&new=6167%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fconfig%2FIPSLCM6%2FSOURCES%2FNEMO&old=5501%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fconfig%2FIPSLCM6%2FSOURCES%2FNEMO

2.3. XIOS modifications

The changes to XIOS are relatively minor. First, they concern the management of the MPI communicator of the ensemble. Each member of a component registers as

an individual component with OASIS. However, XIOS needs a communicator that groups all the members of the same component. To do this, it requires to OASIS to return the communicator based on the list of the identifiers of several of the members, using the new "oasis_get_multi_intracomm" function which was developed for this purpose at the request of this project and then integrated into the official OASIS sources.

In addition, some modifications to a file (onetcf4.cpp) were necessary to allow an output file to be modified when adding missing member data later on (running by member pools, explained later in the document). All the modifications made to XIOS in the context of this project can be consulted here:

https://forge.ipsl.jussieu.fr/igcmg/changeset?reponame=&new=6168%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodels%2FXIOS&old=5501%40CONFIG_DEVT%2FIPSLCM6.5_work_ENSEMBLES%2Fmodels%2FXIOS

2.4. OASIS modifications

In IPSL model, OASIS is in charge of managing MPI communicators (Figure 3) :

MPI local communicators of the models are created by OASIS at the initialization phase of the coupling to allow internal communication into the models.

MPI inter-communicators between XIOS and the models are created by OASIS at the initialization phase to allow communication between XIOS and the models. This feature is only possible between two components (for example XIOS and a single model) whereas we need XIOS to be able to communicate with all the members of a component. For that, it is needed to create a MPI communicator containing all member processes of a component, to allow collective calls to XIOS subroutines.

Figure 3 : Handling of MPI communicators in one instance of IPSL model

This functionality was missing in OASIS and has been added in OASIS3-MCT by the Oasis development team. `oasis_get_multi_intracomm` and `oasis_get_multi_intercomm` subroutines have been created and integrated into the new release OASIS3-MCT_5.0.

3. Ensembles simulations with the IPSL model

3.1. Ensemble simulations with selection process: definition

Ensemble simulations considered in this study consist in running several instances/members in parallel and periodically selecting and cloning (with perturbation) trajectories which go in the favored direction (measured by a score function). For example, on the figure 4, there are 3 members with 3 different trajectories: according to the score realized by each trajectory after a simulation period, we choose to kill the 1st one, clone the 2nd one and extend the 3rd one, all this in order to have always 3 members on the following period.

Figure 4 : Example of selection of trajectories

3.2. Running environment

The IPSL model uses the libGCM tool as a running environment: it is a shell script library developed at IPSL which allows simulations to be carried out on different computing centers. This tool launches a main calculation job which will automatically

resubmit itself until the desired period is simulated. At a given frequency, this main job launches secondary post-processing jobs which process the files produced by the model in order to save these data on an archive space on the one hand and to generate analysis products on the other hand. From the reference version of the libIGCM tool, several modifications were necessary in order to be able to manage "ensemble simulations" type. These modifications concern following topics:

- management of execution of all instances of IPSL-CM model over a period in the same main computing Job.
- division of members into pools of members, with handling the number of pools and size of pools within libIGCM parameters. The members of a pool run at the same time, the pools run sequentially one after the other, in the same computing Job on a given period.
- handling of restart files to allow, at a libIGCM level, the continuation or the stop of a member.
- use of an external tool into libIGCM library for the selection.
- handling of perturbation to be applied (or not) to a specific member at libIGCM level.

Figure 5 : Steps of selection and perturbation protocol in ensemble simulation

4. Application cases

The use of this new tool for managing ensembles simulations with the IPSL model has been used in several applications. These applications allowed us to test and validate the tool on realistic configurations and to evaluate the gain/loss brought by the tool on different use cases. The parameters to be studied in the context of this assessment are the number of inodes generated, the total time-to-solution (time needed to run all the members over a given period) as well as computing hours. The total time-to-solution can be determined as the time spent to run each of the pools sequentially (time-to-solution of a pool), to which must be added the time spent between the pools (inter-pool time) as shown in figure 6. This time spent between pools comes essentially from the management of input files and restart files of the model.

Figure 6 : Example of time-to-solution of ensembles workflow with pool size of 2

4.1. Reconstruction of paleoclimate and historical periods using data assimilation (M. Khodri, IPSL/LOCEAN)

Although complex to implement, the assimilation of climate proxies into climate models is a powerful means of identifying the key mechanisms of climate change described in the last millennium. To date, no such exercise with a coupled general circulation model has been successful, due to a filter degeneracy problem associated with solving a

large problem with an insufficient number of particles (or members of a large ensemble). Theoretically, the solution is to significantly increase the number of particles. We have recently developed an approach to overcome this problem and limit the high computational costs associated with the use of GCMs. This approach is based on the use of an auxiliary particle filter integrated in the production line of the IPSL model, in its version adapted to ensemble simulations as described previously in this document. This data assimilation protocol has also been used for reconstruction of the historical period. The machine used here is TGCC Irene AMD Rome (2292 computing nodes AMD Rome Epyc, 2.6 GHz, 128 computing cores/node).

4.1.1. Reconstruction of 1500 years of paleoclimate (500 – 2014)

The new SIR-LIM assimilation method allows us to guide the coupled model simulations while preserving physical consistency along the assimilation process. Such a climate reconstruction covering the last 1500 years from AD 500 to 2014 will uncover new mechanisms underlying climate variability and new sources of predictability that may come into play in the coming years or century. The objective here is to allow the production of the particle filter with the IPSL climate model over the last millennium and the assimilation of climate variables deduced from natural archives (from isotopic measurements in corals, speleothems, marine sediments, etc.) collected at the surface of the globe from the PAGES2K database. The version of the model used in this project corresponds to the very low resolution version (VLR) of IPSL-CM6A model. It is a light configuration of the CMIP6 version of the IPSL model that allows us to perform long ensemble simulations to study paleoclimate variability. In this version, the atmospheric horizontal resolution is reduced from 144x142 horizontal resolution and 79 vertical levels (LR) to 96x96 (~ 400 km) with 59 vertical levels while the nominal eORCA 1° ocean grid is reduced to ORCA 2° resolution (~200 km). All codes in the coupled model have a checkpoint-restart system. The libGCM set of scripts allows decomposing long simulations (several tens or hundreds of years). The model is restarted each year of simulation, with writing and saving of a checkpoint. Each job chains several years, so as to have jobs in the machine about 24 hours. The jobs are chained over several weeks to reach the desired simulation length. One instance of the IPSL-CM6A-VLR model run on 843 Irene AMD Rome computing cores at 48 Simulated Year Per Day (SYPD) using 47 MPI process x 16 OpenMP threads for LMDZ atmospheric model, 90 MPI process for NEMO oceanic model and 1 XIOS server (see Figure 6.).

Figure 6 : IPSL model ocean-atmosphere configuration at very low resolution

The objective here is both to run (and synchronize) 80 members of this model in order to use data assimilation methods (SIR-LIM-Analogues) to select after every simulated year and write out data on the fly into one single file thanks to XIOS. We have divided the 80 members into 8 pools of 10 members on 8 421 cpu cores. Thanks to aggregated output we gained a factor 80 on the number of generated inodes. The time to solution for one pool over 1 year period is 30 min and does not depend on the size of the pool (see Table 1). Time to solution for all members depends on the number of pools (and size of pools) and we can see we obtain the final solution 10 times faster with 8 pools of 10 members in comparison with 80 pools of 1 member (i.e, as performed before ensembles development). An additional cost in time has been noticed between 2 consecutive pools, mainly due to the handling of restart files, selection and perturbation of the members: this additional cost strongly depends on the size of the pool. This inter-pool time has a significant impact on the total time-to-solution and consequently on the number of computing hours.

Number of pools	Size of one pool	Nb of cores	Time to solution for 1 pool for 1 year period	Total time to solution for 1 year (with no inter-pool)	Inter-pool time	Total time to solution for 1 year period (with inter-pool)	Number of computing hours for 1 year period
80	1	843	30 min	40 h		40 h	33 720 h
40	2	1 685	30 min	20 h	3 min	21.9 h	36 985 h
16	5	4 211	30 min	8 h	5 min	9.2 h	38 951 h
10	8	6 737	30 min	5 h	8 min	6.1 h	41 769 h
8	10	8 421	30 min	4 h	12 min	5.3 h	45 473 h

Table 1 : Time to solution and computing hours with IPSL-CM6A-VLR model configuration

Besides the reduction of generated inodes, the use of one single file is very useful for analyzing the results. These developments could also be useful for low resolution models (that use few cores) to allow them to apply for computing hours that are usually reserved for applications using several thousands cores (e.g. PRACE).

4.1.2. Reconstruction of last 130 years of historical period (1880 – 2014)

The protocol described above has been also used to simulate the historical period (1880-2014). The version of the model corresponds to the low resolution version (LR) of IPSL-CM6A model. This configuration has been intensively used within the CMIP6 exercise. In this version of the model, the atmospheric horizontal resolution is 144x142 (~ 200 km) and 79 vertical levels while the oceanic horizontal resolution is eORCA 1° (~100 km). As mentioned before, all codes in the coupled model have a checkpoint-restart system every simulated year and the libGCM set of scripts allows decomposing long simulations (several tens or hundreds of years). One member of the IPSL-CM6A-LR model runs on 1857 Irene AMD Rome computing cores at 28 Simulated Year Per Day (SYPD) using 71 MPI process x 8 OpenMP threads for LMDZ atmospheric model, 360 MPI process for NEMO oceanic model and 1 XIOS server (see Figure 7.). Because of low memory bandwidth, Irene-Rome requires us to depopulate, that is to say to use 2 computing cores per process/thread in order to obtain acceptable performances in terms of time to solution.

Figure 7 : IPSL model ocean-atmosphere configuration at low resolution

The objective here is both to run (and synchronize) 80 members of this model in order to use data assimilation methods (SIR-LIM-Analogues) to select members after every simulated year and write out data on the fly into one single file thanks to XIOS. We have divided the 80 members into 10 pools of 8 members on 15 360 computing cores.

Here we limit the number of members per pool to 8, because it is difficult to run jobs with more than 15 000 cores on the machine. Thanks to aggregated output we gained a factor 80 on the number of generated inodes. The time to solution for one pool over 1 year period is 50 min and does not depend on the size of the pool (see Table 2). Time to solution for all members depends on the number of pools (and size of pools) and we can see we obtain the final solution about 8 times faster with 10 pools of 8 members in comparison with 80 pools of 1 member (i.e, as performed before ensembles development). As in the paleoclimate experiment, an additional cost in time has been noticed between 2 consecutive pools, mainly due to the handling of restart files, selection and perturbation of the members: this additional cost (called inter-pool time) is strongly depending on the size of the pool. This inter-pool time has a significant impact on the total time-to-solution and consequently on the number of computing hours.

Number of pools	Size of one pool	Nb of cores	Time to solution for 1 pool for 1 year period	Total time to solution for 1 year period (with no inter-pool)	Inter-pool time	Total time to solution for 1 year period (with inter-pool)	Number of computing hours for 1 year period
80	1	1857	50 min	66 h		66 h	123 800 h
40	2	3714	50 min	33 h	5 min	36.5 h	135 870 h
20	4	7927	50 min	16 h	8 min	19.2 h	152 198 h
16	5	9473	50 min	13 h	10 min	15.8 h	149 989 h
10	8	15360	50 min	8 h	15 min	10.5 h	162 560 h

Table 2 : Time to solution and computing hours with IPSL-CM6A-LR model configuration

4.2. Extreme events (heat waves) (R. Noyelle, IPSL/LSCE)

The study of extreme climate events suffers from an essential flaw: these events are by nature rare. Whether in reanalysis data or in climate models, any time series, even a long one, shows only a few extreme events. For example, a pre-industrial climate simulation over a period of 1000 years may only show, on average, one heat wave. In order to study these rare events, we use here rare event algorithm methods: the idea is to induce the model to show more rare events while controlling the way it is modified in order to obtain both physically realistic trajectories and to estimate the real probabilities associated with the simulated events. More precisely, we wish to apply a rare event algorithm to the IPSL atmospheric model in order to simulate unprecedented heat waves over Western Europe under different anthropogenic forcing conditions. The aim is to better understand how the dynamics leading to heat

waves change with climate change and to specify the return times of extreme temperature events under different emission scenarios.

The version of the model used in this project corresponds to the low resolution version (LR) of IPSL-CM6A model in its atmosphere-surface only configuration. In this version, the atmospheric horizontal resolution is 144x142 horizontal resolution (~ 200 km) and 79 vertical levels. All codes in the model have a checkpoint-restart system. The libGCM set of scripts allows decomposing long simulations (several tens or hundreds of years). The model is restarted for each period of simulation, with writing and saving of a checkpoint. Each job chains several simulated days. One member of the IPSL-CM6A-LR atmosphere-surface model runs on 1138 Irene AMD Rome computing cores at 28 Simulated Year Per Day (SYPD) using 71 MPI process x 8 OpenMP threads for LMDZ atmospheric model and 1 XIOS server (see Figure 8.). Because of low memory bandwidth, Irene-Rome requires us to depopulate, that is to say to use 2 computing cores per process/thread in order to obtain acceptable performances in terms of time to solution.

Figure 8 : IPSL model atmosphere-surface only configuration at low resolution

The objective here is both to run (and synchronize) 100 members of this model in order to select every 5 simulated days the "best" trajectories that can cause heat waves. We run 10 pools of 10 members on 11 362 computing cores but we have realized that the cost, in terms of computing hours, is very high, especially because 1) there are many stops and restarts and 2) the time of a 5 day run is small compared to the time spent between 2 consecutive runs (because of the additional cost mainly due to the handling of restart files, selection and perturbation of the members). It is therefore not necessary in this case, neither to depopulate, nor to use many cores per member. We decided not to activate the OpenMP parallelization and thus reduce by a factor of 16 the number of cores used (712 computing cores for one pool instead of 11 362 cores). With this readjustment the time to solution for one pool of the model becomes 600s on 712 computing cores (instead of 85s on 11 362 cores) and the number of computing hours needed to perform a simulation period is reduced by a factor 4 (see Table 3). Output data is written out on the fly into one single file thanks to XIOS and consequently we gained a factor 100 on the number of generated inodes.

Number of pools	Size of one pool	Nb cores	Time to solution for 1 pool for 1 period (5 days)	Total time to solution for 1 period (with no inter-pool)	Inter-pool time	Total time to solution for 1 period (with inter-pool))	Number of computing hours for 1 period (5 days)
10	10	11362	85 s	14 min	2 min	32 min	6059 h
10	10	712	600 s	100 min	2 min	118 min	1400 h

Table 3 : Time to solution and computing hours with IPSL-CM6A-LR model atmosphere-surface only configuration

5. Conclusions and perspectives

The development of an ensemble management tool for the IPSL model has been a success. The development itself is a good example of collaboration between the OASIS and XIOS tools (and development teams). We then achieved our initial goal of reducing the number of inodes produced during the simulation of ensembles, in order to satisfy the criteria of the computing centers. In addition to that, the time needed to perform the simulations of all the members has been greatly reduced. This feature is very useful, especially for very low resolution model configurations, to target large computational allocations usually reserved for applications using several thousand computational cores. For the future, it could be useful to be able to perform reductions/operations between members: the tool presented in this report is based on XIOS2 and allows to do this, but only between members of the same pool. On the other hand, such operations could have an impact on computational performance, as they would be performed on the model/client side and would therefore require synchronization of all members. Ideally, asynchronous services dedicated to this type of operation would allow this to be done: this is currently not available in the XIOS2 version but will be in the upcoming XIOS3 version.

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